

THE INFLUENCE OF NATURALISM AND SOCIETY IN THOMAS HARDY'S WORKS

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Annotation

Thomas Hardy is often classified as one of the most prominent writers of the Victorian era, renowned for his exploration of the darker aspects of human life. His works, particularly his novels, are heavily influenced by Naturalism, a literary movement that emphasizes the power of the environment, heredity, and social circumstances on human behavior. Hardy's portrayal of life and society often challenges the idealistic portrayals popular in his time, delving into themes of fatalism, social constraints, and human suffering. Through his complex characters and intricate narratives, Hardy critiques the social structures of Victorian England while exploring the impact of these forces on individuals' lives.

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Naturalism, which emerged as a response to Realism in the late 19th century, focuses on how individuals are shaped by their environment, their genetic inheritance, and their social and economic conditions. Writers like Émile Zola, who is often seen as the father of Naturalism, were preoccupied with showing how uncontrollable forces—such as poverty, societal expectations, and the natural world—dictate the fates of characters.

Hardy's early works, like *Tess of the d'Urbervilles* (1891) and *Jude the Obscure* (1895), reflect the tenets of Naturalism. His characters are often driven by forces beyond their control—social restrictions, economic conditions, and the oppressive expectations of society. For example, Tess, in *Tess of the d'Urbervilles*,

is a product of her social class and her environment. Despite her natural beauty and intelligence, Tess is condemned by the rigid moral framework of Victorian society, which ultimately leads to her tragic downfall. Hardy's representation of Tess is not just as a victim of her circumstances but also as a symbol of the harshness of social conventions and the failure of institutions such as marriage, religion, and class.

Similarly, in *Jude the Obscure*, Hardy presents Jude Fawley as a character trapped by his lower-class status and the constraints placed on him by society. His aspirations to become a scholar are thwarted not only by his own social class but also by the puritanical views that dominate the community around him. Jude's eventual tragic end reflects Hardy's critique of the moral and educational systems of the time, as well as his broader condemnation of the social forces that prevent individuals from realizing their full potential.

Society and Social Critique

While Naturalism is a major influence on Hardy's works, his writing also offers a profound social critique. Hardy was deeply critical of the social hierarchies that governed Victorian society. His portrayal of class divisions, gender inequality, and the restrictive roles placed on women speaks to his disillusionment with the social structure of his time. In novels like *Far from the Madding Crowd* (1874) and *The Return of the Native* (1878), Hardy examines the rigid social roles that characters must navigate and the repercussions of defying these roles.

In *Far from the Madding Crowd*, the character of Bathsheba Everdene challenges traditional notions of femininity by asserting her independence and rejecting the advances of men who seek to control her. Bathsheba's actions, though bold for a woman in Victorian England, ultimately lead to personal suffering. Hardy uses her as a vehicle for exploring the tensions between social expectation and personal desire, offering a critique of the limited roles available to women in his society. Bathsheba's struggle can be seen as a reflection of Hardy's broader concern with the restrictions imposed by social class and gender norms.

In *The Return of the Native*, Hardy again critiques the rigid roles of society through the tragic relationships between his characters. Eustacia Vye, one of Hardy's most complex female characters, is driven by her desire to escape the dull and limiting life in Egdon Heath. Her ambitions are stifled by the constraints of her social class and the expectations of the rural community, which ultimately leads to her tragic end. Through Eustacia's story, Hardy critiques the suffocating nature of small-town life and the inability of individuals to escape the forces that define their roles.

The Role of Nature in Hardy's Novels

Another significant element of Hardy's Naturalism is his depiction of the **natural world**. Hardy often uses nature as a metaphor for the harsh and indifferent forces that govern human existence. His settings, such as the desolate Egdon Heath in *The Return of the Native* or the rugged, unforgiving landscapes in *Tess of the d'Urbervilles*, reflect the moral and emotional desolation of his characters. Nature is not portrayed as a nurturing force, but as something that often mirrors or amplifies the emotional and existential turmoil of the human characters.

In Hardy's view, nature is indifferent to human suffering. It does not provide solace or comfort but rather reflects the bleakness of human existence. In *Tess of the d'Urbervilles*, Tess's tragic fate is paralleled by the indifferent forces of nature, which continue unabated in the face of her suffering. In the novel's closing scenes, Hardy's depiction of the natural world underscores the futility of human effort in the face of overwhelming, impersonal forces.

Thomas Hardy's works are heavily influenced by Naturalism, reflecting the key tenets of the movement through his depiction of characters shaped by their social environment and personal heredity. At the same time, Hardy uses his novels and poetry to critique the oppressive social systems of his time, particularly the rigid class structures and gender expectations that govern individuals' lives. His works are a profound commentary on the interplay between human agency, social

forces, and the indifferent power of nature, making them an enduring reflection of the complex realities of Victorian society.

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3. Zola, Émile. *The Experimental Novel*. (1880).
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4. Pite, Ralph. *Thomas Hardy and the Natural World*. (2006).
This book explores Hardy's use of nature as a backdrop for his critiques of society and human suffering, reflecting Naturalist ideas of fate and the environment's power over human life.